

From Individual Action to Collective Hives: Identifying Gains in Community-oriented Urban Heating Transitions

Susan Ruinaard^{*1,4}, BinBin Pearce^{†1}, Juliana Goncalves^{‡2}, Neelke Doorn^{§1}, Jaap Witte^{¶4}
and Trivik Verma^{||3}

¹Faculty of Technology, Policy and Management, Delft University of Technology

²Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment, Delft University of Technology

³Bristol Digital Futures Institute and School for Policy Studies, University of Bristol

⁴Generation.Energy, The Hague, The Netherlands

GISRUK 2025

Summary

To support just urban energy transitions, we propose a flexible "policy rationale" framework tailored to the level of communal engagement. This framework develops decarbonisation scenarios along an engagement spectrum, evaluating trade-offs between decarbonisation gains, investment costs, and social justice for The Hague, The Netherlands. Through a capability-sensitive approach, local vulnerabilities were identified. We show that while individual approaches offer higher gains per household, they leave vulnerable communities behind. Alternatively, community-oriented solutions address social justice concerns, requiring limited investments and decarbonising communities that otherwise cannot. Therefore, policy efforts should focus on reducing barriers for those communities, to foster long-term and just decarbonisation.

KEYWORDS: urban heating transition, energy justice, capability approach, public policy, regionalization.

1 Introduction

In the face of climate change, energy transitions propelled to the top of political agendas (Sequeira et al., 2024), alongside growing energy poverty concerns. Mulder et al. (2023) reveal that 7%

*s.ruinaard@hotmail.com

†b.j.pearce-1@tudelft.nl

‡j.e.goncalves@tudelft.nl

§n.doorn@tudelft.nl

¶jaap@generation.energy

||trivik.verma@bristol.ac.uk

of Dutch households are energy-poor, with 48% unable to participate in the energy transition independently.

Despite governmental efforts, socio-spatial inequalities are growing in European cities (Cassiers and Kesteloot, 2012), where economic disparities manifest as unequal access to opportunities in residential energy transitions (Kraaijvanger et al., 2023). This exacerbates the cost of living (Haffner and Hulse, 2019) and reinforces patterns of urban inequality (Bouzarovski and Simcock, 2017; Garvey et al., 2022). While the inability to pay energy bills is a critical aspect of energy poverty, it only scratches the surface of a more complex issue. Multifaceted personal, societal, and environmental drivers contribute to heightened socio-spatial vulnerability to energy poverty beyond energy efficiency, affordability, financial capacity, and home ownership (Robinson et al., 2019), leaving several communities behind in transitions tailored to individuals.

To facilitate just, effective, and inclusive decarbonisation processes, municipalities must shift from individual solutions to actively brokering communities to adopt solutions on a larger scale. As energy justice and equity considerations have gained prominence in decision-making (Baker et al., 2023), effective policies should address the intricate dynamics that perpetuate socio-spatial inequalities and energy poverty (Bouzarovski and Simcock, 2017; Garvey et al., 2022). By understanding local barriers to transition, policymakers can identify and support communities at risk of being excluded from the decarbonisation process, where tailored strategies ensure equitable access.

We propose a “policy rationale” framework that adapts flexibly to communal engagement levels. Using this framework, we develop decarbonisation scenarios across a spectrum of engagement – from individual to beehive – and measure trade-offs between decarbonisation gains, investment costs, and social justice, assuming local communities successfully transition with municipal support. We use The Hague’s heating transition as a case study.

2 Policy rationales

To illustrate societal outcomes between individual approaches and collective hives, we design, develop and evaluate policy rationales (PR) to inform residential heating transition plans. A PR reflects a transition pathway, where municipal support enables communities to decarbonise.

PR1: Business-as-usual – Providing Individual Subsidies

The Netherlands (and many countries globally) rely on individual subsidies for retrofitting the housing stock (Kraaijvanger et al., 2023; Mulder et al., 2023) – despite evidence of socio-spatial exclusion of vulnerable groups (Reames, 2016). Therefore, *individual subsidies* is evaluated as baseline PR.

PR2: Alleviating Energy Poverty

With energy justice and equity being a key policy priority (Baker et al., 2023), we measure the gains of providing transition support to local communities experiencing energy poverty.

PR3: Targeting Housing Cooperations

Housing cooperations provide housing for low-income groups, and are required to meet sustainability targets despite financial constraints (Boezeman and De Vries, 2019), where residents cannot transition independently. Nearby homeowners and private renters face similar challenges through personal barriers. Measuring gains for these spatially co-located communities illustrates where policies can link with institutions to transition.

3 Socio-spatial Alignment

To enable PR assessments, localised realities are identified that risk being overlooked by the current practice of focusing on administrative boundaries, characterised by aggregation problems such as MAUP, aggregation bias, and NEAP (Duque et al., 2007; Kwan, 2018). Therefore, a bottom-up approach is taken to cluster streets into localities, based on coherence in the built environment and sociodemographic characteristics.

The street-level dataset is created with openly available data sets by Kadaster (2024); Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek (2024); Rijksoverheid (2024); Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed (2019), described in Figure 1.

The data processing resulted in 39 indicators for approximately 15.000 streets. For socio-spatial alignment, we employed the Max- P regionalisation algorithm from PySAL’s *sport* library (Feng et al., 2021, 2022) - which ensures minimal spatial aggregation, minimal aggregation bias, data dictating the shape, valid statistical inference, and estimation precision (Duque et al., 2011; Wei et al., 2020).

Using an aggregation threshold of at least 500 dwellings, we found 426 localities compared to 114 administrative neighbourhoods - providing a finer resolution to identify socio-spatial disparities, while maintaining workable units for planners and policymakers.

To obtain locality values (I_l), each street-level indicator (i_s) is weighted by the number of dwellings in the corresponding street segment (d_s) and summed, divided by the number of dwellings in the locality (D_l):

$$I_l = \frac{\sum_{s \in S_l} i_s \cdot d_s}{\sum_{d \in D_l} d_s} \quad (1)$$

Figure 1: Data processing to create the street-level data set for Max-P regionalisation, consisting of sociodemographic, energy and built environment characteristics

4 Framework to Evaluate Policy Rationales

4.1 Policy Indicators

Vulnerability

In our dataset, we identified personal and built environmental characteristics that increase local vulnerability – using ‘conversion factors’ of the capability approach (see Robeyns and Byskov (2023) for background) and literature on energy poverty (Robinson et al., 2019; Mulder et al., 2023; Gouveia et al., 2019; Kraaijvanger et al., 2023), further supplemented to fit the Dutch heating transition context (Table 1). Vulnerability is not inherent to persons – it reflects possible barriers as complex skills are needed to transition.

Table 1: Socio-spatial vulnerability factors in access to heating transition opportunities

Indicator	Vulnerability factors (v)
Age	0-15 year-olds, 15-25 year-olds, 65 and older
Migration background	EU, non-EU
Household structure	Single person, Single parent
Income	State benefit recipients, Property valuation
Homeownership structure	Private renting, Different owners, Mixed-use environment
Energy	Energy inefficient dwellings (labels C-D and E-G), Gas usage
Dwelling type	Apartments, Monumental dwellings

To calculate the local vulnerability level (V_l), these 17 vulnerability factors (v_l) were standardised using fractional rank and aggregated by taking the mean:

$$V_l = \text{mean}(\text{fractional_rank}(v_l)) \quad (2)$$

Decarbonisation

The potential for decarbonisation (D_l) is linked to the actual gas usage of dwellings in 2022. For each locality (l), this potential is calculated by multiplying the average household gas consumption per street ($g_{s,l}$) by the number of dwellings ($d_{s,l}$), summed across all streets in the locality.

$$D_l = \sum_{s=1}^{n_c} (g_{s,l} \times d_{s,l}) \quad (3)$$

Investment

The investment costs for decarbonisation (I_l) are equal to the sum of insulation and new heating system costs of all dwellings (j) in the corresponding locality (l).

The insulation expenses ($c_{j,l}^{\text{ins}}$) entail the investment needed to upgrade the energy label to B+, as a proxy - since energy label improvement is done by energy-efficiency measures beyond insulation. The costs were estimated using the current energy label and dwelling type, using metrics from the VestaMAIS model by Planbureau voor de Leefomgeving (2012).

The heating system costs ($c_{j,l}^{\text{heat}}$) are determined with the technology assigned to each neighbourhood (Den Haag, 2022), adjusted for the current adaptation of gas-free alternatives ($p_{j,l}$) (Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek, 2023).

$$I_l = \sum_{j=1}^{d_l} \left(c_{j,l}^{\text{ins}} + c_{j,l}^{\text{heat}} \times \frac{100 - p_{j,l}}{100} \right) \quad (4)$$

4.2 Catchment Area of Policy Rationales

General policies translate into spatial distributive patterns, intended or not. Therefore, we define the catchment areas of our PRs beforehand – described in Figure 2. For individual subsidies, we use solar PV adoption (Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek, 2021); for energy poverty Mulder et al. (2023)’s indicator (CBS and TNO, 2023), and for housing cooperations zipcode data (Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek, 2024).

Figure 2: Data processing for PR indicators and creating policy catchment areas

4.3 Navigating Trade-offs within Policy Rationales

To understand where cost-efficient decarbonisation is possible while being sensitive to local vulnerability, the policy indicators are mapped as a ternary composition (Figure 3) – using the R Tricolore library (Schöley, 2025). The ternary diagram illustrates trade-offs between the indicators (standardised with percentiles), with the colour assigned based on the location in the diagram. Vivid vertice colours represent a strong balance towards one indicator, whereas mixed colours indicate a mix of two indicators. The greyish middle represents a relatively equal balance (Schöley, 2021).

The overall city-scale impacts of a PR are assessed as coverage of each indicator compared to The Hague, using radar plots for a comprehensive overview.

Figure 3: A ternary diagram and corresponding map showing the balance between vulnerability, decarbonisation and investment for each locality. Localities on the pink-green axis, such as the highlighted locality, represent local cost-effective decarbonisation while covering high vulnerability

5 Results

The societal effects of the PRs are presented as policy sheets, which include maps of vulnerability, decarbonisation and investment (as deciles), with corresponding ternary maps and city coverage radar plots. The sheets for individual subsidies, energy poverty and housing cooperations are in Figures 4, 5 and 6, respectively.

The spatiality of policy effects from individual subsidies (Figure 4) is confined in the outer Eastern, Southern and coastal areas. The East and South (Ypenburg-Leidschenveen, Loosduinen, Hoge Veld and Lage Veld) are characterised by newer urban developments, built with gas-free heating solutions and good insulation standards. This leaves residents less vulnerable through the built environment and requires minimal heating upgrades. In contrast, the coastal areas (Scheveningen and Segbroek) are characterised by large, detached and old dwellings, explaining the high potential for decarbonisation, paired with high costs. Although these residents experience barriers through the built environment, they were able to adopt solar panels being homeowners in (semi)detached dwellings. Generally, the personal determinants of vulnerability are relatively low.

Figure 4: Policy Sheet: Individual Subsidies

An approach for alleviating energy poverty (Figure 5) reaches areas with an inverted spatial pattern compared to the previous rationale - corresponding to Den Haag Zuidwest, Schilderswijk and Mariahoeve, characterised by high building densities, multi-level apartment buildings and smaller dwelling floor areas. This results in lower decarbonisation gains, as smaller buildings require less gas for heating. This does not detract from the reality that energy bills are more pressing. With high vulnerability in these areas, more people are prone to experience transition-related barriers, possibly being left behind in the decarbonisation process and experiencing energy poverty in the future.

Figure 5: Policy Sheet: Energy Poverty

Housing cooperations own dwellings across The Hague, reflected in the spatiality of policy effects (Figure 6). The potential decarbonisation is lower, explained by smaller dwellings, a mix of newer and older buildings, and progress towards sustainability targets. As social housing is available in socially disadvantaged neighbourhoods, this rationale largely covers vulnerability.

Figure 6: Policy Sheet: Housing Cooperations

6 Discussion

In this study, we aimed to illustrate the benefits of shifting from individual energy transition approaches to collective ones – and assessed trade-offs in decarbonisation potential, vulnerability coverage, and investment costs for three policy rationales.

The analysis found that cost-effective decarbonisation while fostering just outcomes is achieved by allocating policy resources to areas where energy poverty persists and housing cooperations are active, institutionally reaching local communities that otherwise cannot transition by themselves. This contrasts the (business-as-usual) approach of providing individual subsidies, characterised by fewer vulnerabilities beyond built environmental complexities – which in turn, lead to high gas usage and investment costs.

Our analysis is situated in the broader discussion of spatial and social justice. We urge municipalities to actively build and support local communities and energy initiatives, overcoming individual transition barriers and ensuring nobody is left behind in the decarbonisation process.

We expect that municipalities can incorporate this framework and model different decarbonisation scenarios to meaningfully identify societal gains of collective approaches. Our next steps entail an analysis of local barriers and how the understanding of those supports the creation of tailored community engagement strategies.

7 Acknowledgements

We want to thank the Generation.Energy team for their industry perspectives on the spatial complexities of the heating transition and municipal policy practices in urban energy transitions.

8 Biography

Susan Ruinaard is a Master's graduate in Engineering & Policy Analysis at Delft University of Technology. Her interests entail the infrastructures and communities that shape our cities, where she explores policies that foster just outcomes through spatial modelling.

BinBin Pearce is an Assistant Professor of Policy Analysis and Design at Delft University of Technology, specialising in energy citizenship and the energy transition, process design for joint problem framing, design thinking for systems transformation, and transdisciplinary methodologies and tools for co-design and co-creation.

Juliana Goncalves is an Assistant Professor of Spatial Planning and Strategy at Delft University of Technology, interested in urban inequalities, spatial justice and just energy transitions. She looks at these questions from a socio-spatial intersectional perspective, combining quantitative and qualitative research methods.

Neelke Doorn is a Professor of Ethics of Water Engineering at Delft University of Technology, where her work centres around moral questions in climate change and policy, for which she combines philosophical approaches with empirical investigations and modelling techniques.

Jaap Witte is an Urban Planner and GIS specialist at Generation.Energy and creates models to support and advise governments in decision-making at the intersection of energy transitions and spatial planning.

Trivik Verma is an Associate Professor of Urban Futures at the Bristol Digital Futures Institute and the School for Policy Studies at the University of Bristol, researching cities, socio-spatial inequalities, energy poverty, and human geography using spatial data science.

References

- Baker, E., et al. (2023). Metrics for Decision-Making in Energy Justice. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 48(1), 737–760, <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-112621-063400>.
- Boezeman, D. & De Vries, T. (2019). Climate proofing social housing in the Netherlands: toward mainstreaming? *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management*, 62(8), 1446–1464, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09640568.2018.1510768>.
- Bouzarovski, S. & Simcock, N. (2017). Spatializing energy justice. *Energy policy*, 107, 640–648, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2017.03.064>.
- Cassiers, T. & Kesteloot, C. (2012). Socio-spatial inequalities and social cohesion in European cities. *Urban Studies*, 49(9), 1909–1924, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0042098012444888>.
- CBS and TNO (2023). Monitor Energiearmoede 2020 <https://www.cbs.nl/nl-nl/maatwerk/2023/04/monitor-energiearmoede-2020>.
- Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek (2021). Percentage woningen met geregistreerde zonnepanelen <https://klimaatmonitor.databank.nl/jive>.
- Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek (2023). Woningen; hoofdverwarmingsinstallaties, wijken en buurten, 2022 https://opendata.cbs.nl/statline/portal.html?_la=nl&_catalog=CBS&tableId=85677NED&_theme=284.
- Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek (2024). Kerncijfers per postcode <https://www.cbs.nl/nl-nl/dossier/nederland-regionaal/geografische-data/gegevens-per-postcode>.
- Den Haag (2022). *Transitievisie warmte Den Haag*. Technical report, Den Haag https://duurzamestad.denhaag.nl/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/Transitievisie_Warmte.pdf.
- Duque, J. C., Anselin, L., & Rey, S. J. (2011). THE MAX-P-REGIONS PROBLEM*. *Journal of Regional Science*, 52(3), 397–419, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9787.2011.00743.x>.
- Duque, J. C., Ramos, R., & Suriñach, J. (2007). Supervised Regionalization Methods: A Survey. *International Regional Science Review*, 30(3), 195–220, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0160017607301605>.
- Feng, X., et al. (2022). spopt: a python package for solving spatial optimization problems in pysal. *Journal of Open Source Software*, 7(74), 3330.
- Feng, X., Gaboardi, J. D., Knaap, E., Rey, S. J., & Wei, R. (2021). pysal/spopt <https://github.com/pysal/spopt>.
- Garvey, A., Norman, J. B., Büchs, M., & Barrett, J. (2022). A “spatially just” transition? A critical review of regional equity in decarbonisation pathways. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 88, 102630, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2022.102630>.

- Gouveia, J. P., Palma, P., & Simões, S. (2019). Energy poverty vulnerability index: A multidimensional tool to identify hotspots for local action. *Energy Reports*, 5, 187–201, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egy.2018.12.004>.
- Haffner, M. E. A. & Hulse, K. (2019). A fresh look at contemporary perspectives on urban housing affordability. *International Journal of Urban Sciences*, 25(sup1), 59–79, <https://doi.org/10.1080/12265934.2019.1687320>.
- Kadaster (2024). BAG GeoPackage <https://www.kadaster.nl/zakelijk/producten/adressen-en-gebouwen/bag-geopackage>.
- Kraaijvanger, C. W., Verma, T., Doorn, N., & Goncalves, J. E. (2023). Does the sun shine for all? Revealing socio-spatial inequalities in the transition to solar energy in The Hague, The Netherlands. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 104, 103245, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2023.103245>.
- Kwan, M.-P. (2018). The Neighborhood Effect Averaging Problem (NEAP): an elusive confounder of the neighborhood effect. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 15(9), 1841, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph15091841>.
- Mulder, P., Longa, F. D., & Straver, K. (2023). Energy poverty in the Netherlands at the national and local level: A multi-dimensional spatial analysis. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 96, 102892, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2022.102892>.
- Planbureau voor de Leefomgeving (2012). Vesta ruimtelijk energiemodel voor de gebouwde omgeving - Data en Methoden <https://www.pbl.nl/publicaties/vesta-ruimtelijk-energiemodel-voor-de-gebouwde-omgeving-data-en-methoden>.
- Reames, T. G. (2016). Targeting energy justice: Exploring spatial, racial/ethnic and socioeconomic disparities in urban residential heating energy efficiency. *Energy Policy*, 97, 549–558, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2016.07.048>.
- Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed (2019). Rijksmonumenten <https://nationaalgeoregister.nl/geonetwork/srv/dut/catalog.search#/metadata/eedd39d6-b427-4e11-90fd-f5054241c3a7>.
- Rijksoverheid (2024). Openbare data energielabels <https://www.ep-online.nl/PublicData>.
- Robeyns, I. & Byskov, M. F. (2023). The Capability Approach. In E. N. Zalta & U. Nodelman (Eds.), *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy*. Metaphysics Research Lab, Stanford University, Summer 2023 edition.
- Robinson, C., Lindley, S., & Bouzarovski, S. (2019). The spatially varying components of vulnerability to energy poverty. *Annals of the American Association of Geographers*, 109(4), 1188–1207, <https://doi.org/10.1080/24694452.2018.1562872>.

- Schöley, J. (2021). The centered ternary balance scheme: A technique to visualize surfaces of unbalanced three-part compositions. *Demographic Research*, *44*, 443–458, <https://doi.org/10.4054/demres.2021.44.19>.
- Schöley, J. (2025). GitHub - jschoeley/tricolore: A flexible color scale for ternary compositions <https://github.com/jschoeley/tricolore>.
- Sequeira, M. M., Gouveia, J. P., & De Melo, J. J. (2024). (Dis)comfortably numb in energy transitions: Gauging residential hard-to-reach energy users in the European Union. *Energy Research Social Science*, *115*, 103612, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2024.103612>.
- Wei, R., Rey, S. J., & Knaap, E. (2020). Efficient regionalization for spatially explicit neighborhood delineation. *International Journal of Geographical Information Science*, *35*(1), 135–151, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13658816.2020.1759806>.